

Third ANNUAL REPORT

for the period ending June 30, 1959

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, *Inc.*

Yarnell, Harry Ervin, 1875-
Papers, 1937-39.
7 ft.

In Library of Congress, Manuscript Division
U. S. Navy officer. Correspondence, reports,
newspapers, clippings, and memorabilia—
give a first-hand account of conditions in the
Far East before and during the renewal of hostilities
between China and Japan, 1937-39,
when Yarnell was Commander-in-Chief of the Asiatic
Fleet.

Unpublished, *English in the Library*. Also
described in the Library's Quarterly Journal of
current acquisitions, v. 11, no. 3 (May 1954)
p. 165.
Gift of Admiral Yarnell, 1954.

1. China - Japanese Conflict, 1937-1945.

MS 59-13
Library of Congress

Hand, Learned, 1872-
Minutes of trials, 1909-24.
3 ft., (ca. 30 items)

In Library of Congress, Manuscript Division.
Judge. Concise summaries of trials in civil,
criminal, and admiralty courts presided over by
Hand as U.S. Judge of the Southern District of
New York.
Unpublished finding aid in the Library.
Gift of Judge Hand, 1955.

MS 59-12
Library of Congress

1. Trials—U.S.

Washington, Booker T. de Silva, 1850?-1915.

Papers, 1882-1912.
443 ft. (ca. 300,000 items)
In Library of Congress, Manuscript Division.
Editorial author, leader in the advancement of the Negro race.
Eleven large correspondence series, with MSS of books, articles and
speeches, printed matter, sermons, reports, and documents. Printing
MSS material relate to Yankovic Institute, Hampton Institute, the
National Negro Business League, and the General Education Board.
Important correspondents include William H. Halliwell, Wallace Hut-
chinson, Andrew Carnegie, George Washington Carter, James C. Clark-
son, James H. Dillard, Frederick Douglass, William E. B. DuBois,
Charles W. Eliot, T. Thomas Fortune, Helen K. Frazier, Abraham
Grant, Leigh Hunt, Seth Low, Fred R. Moore, Robert R. Moton, E.

(Continued on next card) MS 50-4

Ashley, Frederick William, 1863-1942.

Material for a history of the Library of Congress, 1850,
7 MS boxes.
In Library of Congress, Manuscript Division.
Librarian and scholar. Superintendent of the Reading Room and
Chief Assistant Librarian of Congress. Much for a Library history.
Typical register in the library.
Transfer from administrative assistant to the Librarian of Con-
gress, 1942.

U. S. Library of Congress—Hist.

Library of Congress

MS 20-1

McClellan, George Brinton, 1865-1940.
Papers, 1838-1922.

6 ft. (ca. 5000 items)

In Library of Congress, Manuscript Division.
U. S. Representative from New York, mayor of
New York City, and professor of economic history at
Princeton. Correspondence, scrapbooks (kept during
student years at Princeton, 1885-1864), diary of
military experiences in World War I, subject file
on military activities to McClellan's political activities,
articles, lectures and other miscellaneous MSS, maps.

Unpublished, *English in the Library*. Also
described in the Library's Quarterly Journal of
current acquisitions, v. 9, no. 3 (May 1952) p. 144.
Information on literary rights available in the
Library of Congress.
Gift of Mrs. McClellan, 1951.

MS 59-14
Library of Congress

Palmer, Theodore Sherman, 1858-1935.

Papers, 1877-1934.
27 ft. (ca. 20,000 items)
In Library of Congress, Manuscript Division.
Orthodontist, widely conventionalized and author. Correspondence,
diaries, drafts of speeches and articles, printed matter, ser-
mons and memoranda books. (Faint) Much of the correspondence
relates to the American Orthodontic Union, which Palmer served
as secretary from 1897 to 1927.
Register published in 1928 by the Library of Congress. Also de-
scribed in the Library's Quarterly Journal of current acquisitions,
v. 11, no. 3 (May 1952) p. 169.
Information on literary rights available in repository.
Gift of Mrs. Palmer, 1937.
1. Orthodontics—Correspondence, reminiscences, etc. 2. American
Orthodontic Union.

Library of Congress MS 50-2

Gage, Thomas, 1731-1787.

Papers, 1748-83.
49 ft.
In William L. Clements Library (Ann Arbor, Mich.) Division of
Manuscripts.
British general; commander-in-chief in North America. Corre-
spondence, in two series: on English service with British officials,
including Secretaries of State and War, the Treasury, the Board of
Trade, the Board of Ordnance and others; and on American service
with colonial governors, Indian superintendents, military engineers,
contractors, and other officials and subordinate officers.
Described most fully in Guide to the manuscript collections in the
William L. Clements Library, compiled by H. H. Kuchan (1942). The
MS in all of the Guide, compiled by W. S. Ewing (1933) contains a full

(Continued on next card) MS 50-5

Third
ANNUAL REPORT

*for the period
ending June 30,
1959*

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, *Inc.*
1025 CONNECTICUT AVENUE, N.W., WASHINGTON, D. C.

Council on Library Resources.

Report. 1st-
1956/57-
Washington.

v. 23 cm. annual.

Report year ends June 30.

1. Library science—Research.

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58-915 rev

Library of Congress

Third
ANNUAL
REPORT

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in 1956 in the District of Columbia, with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

The Council conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

THE COUNCIL'S THIRD YEAR

During its third year, the period from July 1, 1958 to June 30, 1959, the Council appropriated sums totaling \$1,275,822 for the support of 35 projects. These projects affected a wide variety of aspects of library work. A number of older projects were concluded. Several of the new allocations were either in continuation of work previously commenced or in substantial support of projects previously under preliminary study. A number were in new areas.

The basic problems of libraries are important to our national life. Numerous and varied, they deal with both the present and future effectiveness with which libraries discharge their functions. Planning the ideal "library of the future" could easily — and perhaps profitably — absorb attention to the exclusion of consideration of present-day problems. A balance must be struck; and the projects described in the following pages include ventures in both areas. Similarly, although the Council prefers to single out problems for attack, yet it not infrequently occurs that a turn of events may offer an opportunity for progress toward the solution of a problem. Again, the projects later described offer examples of both approaches.

There are kinds of library problems with which the Council cannot deal. These are typically those in which no research or new approach is proposed. They include the local needs of libraries for buildings, books and staff or other facilities, the satisfaction of which would have no general effect upon library work as a whole. In addition to these, the Council in general avoids bibliographic and

microfilming projects, to the extent that these are unlikely to provide solutions to general problems.

The Council welcomes proposals for basic research in the processes of distribution, organization, storage and communication of knowledge as affecting libraries; proposals for technological development looking to the improvement of the physical-mechanical apparatus of library work and for refinement of method and bases for coordination of effort holding promise of overall improvement.

At the close of its second year the Council entered into a review of its program policy. From this review there resulted the formal statement shown in an appendix.

VERNER W. CLAPP
President

IMPLEMENTATION OF PROGRAM POLICY

A serious attack upon the problems of libraries might conceivably require, as a starting point, an inventory of such problems. But an attempt to make such an inventory quickly discloses that a mere listing does not provide an adequate guide to a program of solutions: the basic problems are intermingled with the trivial, and the enduring with the transient; while those relations fail to appear by which problems are apparently inextricably entangled in a web of practice dictated in part by exterior conditions.

A better method is through an attempt to perceive problems as parts of a complex related to function. It is at times possible in this manner to detect sequences of operations which together constitute or create the problem which calls for study. Often what had seemed to be an important problem turns out to be merely the reflection of an underlying situation to which attention should be turned. For example, the reproduction of catalog cards constitutes a typical library problem — but the operation is in reality an aspect of the larger problem with respect to the efficient dissemination and local availability of bibliographic information. Further examination shows that though the techniques for catalog card reproduction are admittedly imperfect, the major losses in efficiency derive not so much from imperfection of these techniques as from lack of general standards in bibliographic matters, deficiencies in applying existing standards, and inaccessibility of existing products at places and times where they are needed. It thus becomes apparent that there is a need for the major improvement of the dissemination of bibliographic information which will simultaneously improve the reproduction of catalog cards.

Microfilm offers another example. It involves many problems. The single matter of the standards which affect its manufacture, processing and use alone occupies the continuing attention of a sectional committee of the

American Standards Association, sponsored by the American Library Association. One reason for the difficulty in solving the problems of microfilm stems from the multiplicity of immediate purposes which this material serves. It is used to save space, to avoid the cost of binding, as a means of preserving the record contained in perishable originals, as a method of consolidating in one place materials of which the originals are scattered, as a means of cheap publication, as the basis for single-copy reprinting, as a method of accurate (facsimile) copying, as a cheap, quick and accurate method of note-taking, as a substitute for interlibrary lending of originals, as a substitute for unavailable originals, and as insurance against inaccessibility of originals.

Many activities surround these various applications. If, however, instead of these subsidiary purposes, which are principally those of library administration, we consider the basic purpose of microfilm, which is that of all library materials, it is recognized that this purpose is solely to provide inquirers with needed information. Existing techniques associated with microfilm are deficient in serving this end. Few inquirers are in a position to make use of microfilm without dependence upon a cumbersome piece of institutional equipment. It may in consequence be predicted that the utility of microfilm would increase enormously and its problems would diminish in proportion, if its use could be liberated from expensive equipment, made comfortable and universally acceptable. Only then could its potentialities be realized for providing a quick, accurate, cheap, convenient and expendable facsimile of a desired source of information.

Examination of the elements of library work thus reveals in almost every case deficiencies in method, equipment, organization for work, or knowledge of the facts which should be brought to bear. These in turn, viewed in the light of the basic purpose involved, are sometimes immediately suggestive of avenues for improvement. But it is also often true that controlling factors, such as the capacities of existing mechanical equipment, the organization of bibliographical services, and the like, are not

easily modified. Then it becomes difficult to identify the key log on which the log jam depends. This is true not only for the improvement of present procedures, but for developments looking to the distant future, in which the nature of the conditions encountered is not yet apparent.

The Council's grants always reflect this hope of striking at basic rather than the merely apparent problems of library work. Even when very small grants have been made each has seemed to possess a relevance and potentiality beyond the immediate terms of its title.

THE PROBLEM OF SIZE

Library work, which deals with individual books and inquirers, is — like other human institutions — subject to the pressures of number, of size imposed by an age in which vast quantities are the rule. Not many hundreds of years ago the learned man knew not only every book in his field but its contents. It was a mark of his learning that he could cite the pertinent passages in all the authors. At that time bibliographies, subject catalogs and indexes were unnecessary. Today, when the literature of many subjects has proliferated beyond the capacity of any one person even to identify the separate works, mechanisms must be adopted to bridge the gap.

The first institutional research libraries in the United States were the college libraries, and the earliest among these was that in Cambridge. In a 1643 description of the first Harvard College building it was remarked that there was "a large Library with some Bookes to it." The "large Library" would have been a room with probably little more than the Reverend John Harvard's gift of approximately three hundred volumes five years earlier. When Yale was founded in 1699 the library, according to one legend, comprised forty folio volumes presented by the founding clergymen. It was not until 1701 that the college received a significantly large gift of books — 160

Yesterday, a bookcase or two — today miles of books

to 170 volumes. The New Jersey College, now known as Princeton, had been established four years before its president was authorized to purchase a bookcase to house its growing accumulation of books. So it was with Brown, with Pennsylvania, with Columbia and others: a room, a bookcase or two, and some books.

These libraries grew slowly in a new world where books were scarce. They had their setbacks, especially from fire and in some instances from the ravages of a revolutionary war. But in 1831 the University of Pennsylvania had 2,000 volumes; Columbia, 4,580; the University of North Carolina, 4,800; Rutgers, 6,500; Georgetown, 7,000; Princeton and the University of Virginia, 8,000; Brown, 11,662; while Yale had 25,500, and Harvard 39,605 volumes. Since then with a fair degree of consistency these libraries have been doubling in size very rapidly. Ten of our oldest university libraries have been doubling approximately every seventeen-and-a-half years. In some of the newer of the great universities — such as California, Chicago, Minnesota and Rochester — the libraries since 1876 have been doubling in size about every nine-and-a-half years. The rate in some of the smaller men's colleges, such as Dartmouth and Williams, has been averaging about once every twenty-two years. The rate for a group of women's colleges, including such institutions as Bryn Mawr and Wellesley, has been every thirteen years since 1876. Although the rate of exponential growth appears to be leveling off in some cases, that may reflect an inability to acquire freely rather than a diminution in the number of new works which should be acquired.*

The rate of growth of the academic research libraries is not simply due to the voracious book-hunger of scholars and the acquisitive instincts of librarians. World publication has been doubling every forty-five years during

*The figures given here are taken from Fremont Rider's *The Scholar and the Future of the Research Library* (New York: 1944), supplemented with statistical information from *College and Research Libraries* (18:50-53, January, 1957), and with information supplied by the Georgetown University Library on its collections.

GROWTH OF AMERICAN COLLEGE AND UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES

AVERAGE
NUMBER OF
VOLUMES
1,000,000

Based on data from F. Rider: *The Scholar and the Future of the Research Library*
Subsequent to 1938, *College and Research Libraries*, Jan. 1957

GROWTH OF 10 LARGE U. S. UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES, 1831-1957

Individual Growth of
Three Components of the Ten

AVERAGE
NUMBER OF
VOLUMES
10,000,000

Based on data from F. Rider: *The Scholar and the Future of the Research Library*
Subsequent to 1938, *College and Research Libraries*, Jan. 1957

the five centuries since Gutenberg and Coster labored — doubling roughly three times as fast as the growth of the world's population. In the United States the population doubled every twenty-five years during the 19th century and since then it has doubled again, but during this century and a half the publication rate in this country has doubled every twenty-two years. The Register of Copyrights, in the *Report of the Librarian of Congress for the Fiscal Year Ending June 30, 1958*,* notes the upward trend in copyright registrations and says: "Registration for 'books' (as defined in the statute) printed in the United States increased to 52,275 from last year's total of 48,811 . . ." In the July 6, 1959 issue of *Publishers' Weekly* it was reported that there were 659 more titles published during the first six months of 1959 than during the comparable period in 1958, when 219 more titles were issued than during the same months the preceding year.

Were there no other considerations, the mere rate of publication and acquisition would create problems of the resultant size of collections. The world's population is laid to rest each generation; the world's books have a way of lingering on. How at one and the same time to extract profit and usefulness from this inheritance of the past and yet to prevent it from clogging the channels of present information is another aspect of the problem.

NEW PROJECTS

As in the previous *Annual Report*, the following record of projects supported by the Council during the past year is presented under headings which categorize the various activities which make up library work. The term *bibliographic access* includes all those means by which the existence and location of a book or other published informational record is made known. This kind of access is

*Library of Congress, Washington: 1959. These figures, of course, do not include material not copyrighted.

primary but is rarely an end in itself. *Physical access* refers to all those means by which the record, once identified, is made available to the inquirer. This is the objective of the entire activity. *Administrative factors* include those requisite arrangements through which bibliographic and physical access are afforded — through library buildings and staff, administrative and professional organization, interlibrary cooperation, standards, training, and the like.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC ACCESS

It has been estimated* that the world's annual production of books is some 320,000 separate titles. To this must be added continuing publications in the form of some 33,000 newspapers and 70,000 periodicals, not to mention other vehicles of information such as maps, music, films, sound-recordings, etc. These do not include "unpublished research reports," house organs and other material of a non-public character. The total of separately identifiable titles of books, articles, reports and reviews is probably in the order of ten million per year!

How, in this welter of publication, can the inquirer identify and locate what is relevant to his search? How can he be sure that he has become aware of the publications essential for his purpose?

These are the problems of bibliographic access. Enormous expenditures of money and man power are poured into the devices for providing solutions. Although both

**Library of Congress Information Bulletin*. 13:43; App. 5. October 25, 1954. There are no truly satisfactory figures on the rate of world publication. The British librarian L. Stanley Jast ("Bibliography and the Deluge: I Accuse", *Library Association Record*, 38:353-360, June 1936) after complaining of the lack of accurate information on rate of publication, said the world rate "cannot be less than 250,000 books a year, and is probably considerably more." As for the number of books since the beginning of printing, he described an estimate of 25,000,000 works or editions of works still in existence as "timid, even though qualified by the words 'at the lowest guess.'"

severally and collectively these devices fail to provide the assurance of completeness which many inquirers seek, they nevertheless in general make the mass of publication manageable, and serve a great need.

The basis on which these devices are established, and the basis on which the inquirer uses them is chiefly that of selection. In some instances geography or language provide criteria for a primary selection — as in the case of national bibliographies. In other instances selection is based on subject interest regardless of language — as in the case of international subject bibliographies. Chronology provides another obvious basis for selection — as in the case of annual bibliographies and indexes. Some bibliographies, however, observe no chronological restrictions and library catalogs employ them as secondary to other criteria.

In the case of libraries (and the catalogs which provide bibliographic access to library collections), the basis of selection is simply the foreseen needs of the class of users which the library hopes to serve. The librarian's function is thus to anticipate the wants of his users and to make provision for bibliographic as well as physical access.

The typical means of bibliographical access is thus through bibliographical record. This takes many forms, the library catalog being one. A short way toward improving bibliographical access might seem, therefore, to be to improve bibliographies. But bibliographies of what? That is not easy to answer. The Council, accordingly, has not generally supported the making of bibliographies, but has awaited occasions when the bibliography involved promises wide and general usefulness. Two such occasions appeared during the year just past. Both involved the construction of union catalogs or lists. In addition, the Council supported several projects for the improvement of devices through which sources of information are identified. The projects in this area are as follows:

Union catalogs and lists.

Shelf-classification in law libraries: assistance toward the development of centralized services.

Book selection in college libraries and other libraries having similar needs: exploration of possible services.

International Inventory of Musical Sources: assistance toward American participation.

Machine indexing: experimental studies.

Union catalogs or lists are catalogs formed by the merging of the catalogs of a number of libraries. Their primary purpose is to show which library or libraries possess a copy of a particular book or a set of a particular periodical. Their importance is obvious for inter-library lending, for ordering photocopies, and as a basis for deciding whether a particular book or periodical should be acquired locally.

Union Catalogs and Lists

Union catalogs also have secondary uses. One of these is in bibliographical work. It is sometimes cheaper to secure from a union catalog a copy of the catalog entry made by another library than catalog the book locally. Similarly, the principal bibliographic facts regarding a periodical may usually be found in a union list of serials. These lists have other bibliographic uses as well. At the present time few union catalogs or lists attempt to arrange their contents by subject. Where this is done the result can be an important aid to learning.

An essential to the establishment of a union catalog or list is that the participating libraries use similar systems of cataloging, at least with respect to the adoption of the main filing entry, and in the case of a union subject catalog, with respect to subject entries also. Such catalogs are, in consequence, one of the results made possible by standardization of cataloging practices.

The papers of public figures of the past, not to mention the other records which are needed as sources for the history of the times in which they are made, have all too frequently been widely dispersed. There are a few concentrated accumulations and collections such as those of the Adams family in the Massachusetts Historical Society, and of Henry George in the New York Public Library. More typical, however, are such instances as the papers of Andrew Carnegie, located in half a dozen

The Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections

institutions, and the papers of Thomas Jefferson, which are dispersed in groups of documents varying from a single piece to collections of perhaps 25,000 items scattered among approximately six hundred individuals and institutions from Australia to Moscow. Much the same situation is true of prominent men whom the United States cannot claim as its own. The papers of James Joyce, for instance, are found in fourteen American libraries, the British Museum, the National Library of Ireland and the City Library in Zurich. Material by Yeats is in at least nine American libraries as well as several Irish institutions. With this dispersal of collections there is always the possibility that even a painstaking scholar may overlook available material, especially if he is breaking new ground.

A union catalog of manuscripts, one that does for this material what the National Union Catalog does for books, is an obvious need and a dream of scholars for three-quarters of a century. Financial and other obstacles hindered realization of the dream.

In 1951 the then recently established Joint Committee on Historical Manuscripts, formed by the Association of American Archivists and the American Association for State and Local History at the suggestion of the American Historical Association, concluded that a union catalog should no longer aim at recording all individual papers, but should seek primarily to record collections along lines which had been shown to be feasible by the Historical Records Survey of the Work Projects Administration during the 1930's. It was apparent that a pre-condition for the establishment of such a catalog was the development of a code of rules for cataloging manuscript collections which might meet with general acceptance and which might fit the varying circumstances of antiquity, form, language, and other factors. Once these conclusions were embodied in a plan the Library of Congress proceeded to the development of a code* which has met with general

*Library of Congress: *Rules for Descriptive Cataloging in the Library of Congress. Manuscripts. Preliminary edition. Preprint of the Rules for Collection of Manuscripts.* [Washington:] September 1954 (10 p., processed).

acceptance. With this as a basis, it was then possible to begin a union catalog when the means should become available. The Council, recognizing both the extraordinary value of such a catalog to the scholarly community and the cooperative nature of the enterprise, made a grant to the Library of Congress for this purpose.

The immediate goal is to bring together, in addition to some 3,000 collections in the Library of Congress, uniform descriptions of some 24,000 known collections in approximately seventy-five cooperating repositories, and to print and sell separate catalog cards for each of these collections, thus enabling any library so desiring to maintain a similar record. Each card will contain, in addition to the description and location of a collection, a listing of the most important persons, organizations, places and subjects figuring in the contents. This will make cross-indexing possible.

In library terminology "serials" comprise continuing publications such as magazines, bulletins, reports or other publications appearing in periodic succession. So numerous are these kinds of publication (they are born at the rate of some 8,000 a year) that they have been estimated to constitute three-fourths of all published work. They are of great importance for all studies, and for some disciplines their value is likely to outweigh that of the monographic literature.

*Third Edition
of the Union
List of
Serials*

It has been estimated that some half million serial titles have appeared since the early 18th century. No library, however large, has been able to assemble even half of the serial titles in existence. In the typical large research library not more than a third of the titles are available in relatively complete runs. Since no library can own more than a fraction of the total, the cooperative use of serials through interlibrary loan is a necessity.

American efforts to produce union lists of serials began as early as 1878. The early efforts were local lists, but in 1927 a *Union List of Serials in Libraries of the United States and Canada* was published. The 1580-page book listed 75,000 titles held by more than 225 American

libraries. A 3065-page 2d Edition, published in 1943, listed 120,000 titles in 650 libraries. A supplement was published in 1946 and another in 1949. The Library of Congress in 1951 began publication of *New Serial Titles*, a periodical with cumulative features listing serials which started publication on or after January 1, 1950. While this was a development of continuing value it did not do away with the need for a new edition of the *Union List of Serials*, the 2d Edition of which is obsolete and out of print.

Meanwhile, the continued rapid proliferation of serials made it obvious that ever more gigantic union lists (the 2d Edition with its supplements weighs 32 pounds) do not constitute a permanent solution. Funds are not available to do the work over again every decade. Accordingly, a Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials, Inc., established to study the problem for the library world generally, planned a solution involving the use of punched cards which would mechanize the *List* and keep it ever current. But nearly three million dollars was needed for this purpose. The Committee, encouraged by the Council, developed an alternative plan: republication of the information contained in the 2d Edition with the inclusion of readily available supplementary information, and the development of *New Serial Titles* as the continuing supplement to it. The Council has made the Committee a grant for this purpose, and the actual work of compilation is being commenced by the Library of Congress under the Committee's supervision.

The 3d Edition of the *Union List of Serials in Libraries in the United States and Canada* which will result from this work will be a book comprising four to five thousand pages. It will contain, consolidated in one alphabet, a record of serials which began publication prior to 1950 held by libraries in the United States and Canada. Part of this information will be taken directly from the 2d Edition and its two supplements. Titles which have not previously been included in the *List* will be taken from the National Union Catalog, the *Southeastern Supplement to the Union List of Serials* and reports from participating

libraries. A checking edition of these titles, estimated at some 15,000 in number, will be sent to about five hundred libraries. The holdings reported will then be added to the main file for inclusion in the 3d Edition. It is hoped that the 3d Edition can be published in 1962.

The Joint Committee proposes, as a method for keeping union listing of information about periodicals up to date and for simultaneously avoiding the costly necessity of a fourth edition, to promote, as a cooperative project on the part of the library world, the completeness and utility of the Library of Congress's *New Serial Titles*.

Bibliographies do not constitute the only means of bibliographic access. A meaningful shelf-arrangement of books by subject provides a useful form of bibliographic access — all the more useful because physical access to the work identified by the subject-arrangement is simultaneous with that identification.

*A Shelf-
Classification
for Legal
Publications*

American libraries typically — with some important exceptions — rely upon shelf-arrangement as a device for access. It is even asserted that the insistence upon a meaningful shelf-classification, with all the hardships which it entails, together with the methods instituted for maintaining, publishing and applying such a classification, constitute a principal American contribution to library work.

Because the development and application of a shelf-classification is costly and requires special facilities, and because a classification quickly becomes a hindrance through obsolescence unless currently maintained, it is unlikely that American libraries would continue to use a close shelf-classification, such as the Dewey Decimal or Library of Congress classifications, were they not able to depend upon central services for such maintenance and application, and for the dissemination of the results.

One subject has been hitherto inadequately served in this respect — the law. Sir Matthew Hale in the 17th and Sir William Blackstone in the 18th century are usually credited with having developed the first systematic presentation of the common law. Their schemata, as well as

subsequent ones, have long since been outgrown. In the United States the classification of law has been discussed at least since 1885, when it was proposed to the American Bar Association that it sponsor preparation of a classification. A number of classifications have been published in the ensuing years. None has ever met with general acceptance for the reason that no central service was available for maintaining the currency of any one of these and for providing law libraries promptly with the results of its application to new books.

For long this was not of great moment. Law libraries were generally self-arranging — an obvious grouping of laws, court-holdings, digests, and the like, by jurisdiction, with alphabetically-arranged collections of treatises and trials, provided for most of the material.

The literature of the law has, however, multiplied like that of almost every other subject. This increase has taken place not only in the extension and multiplication of the great series in which legal information was previously usually found, but in thousands of separate documents on separate subjects. If these are to be usefully arranged on the shelves, a classification is needed. To make the classification available, the results of its application need to be published in a form convenient for use.

The Library of Congress, whose Law Library is one of the world's great collections of legal literature, maintains the most extensive shelf-classification scheme and through its catalog cards provides the results of the application of the scheme to other libraries. The national library is therefore a natural source for such services, but it had not, for the very reasons mentioned, developed its own shelf-classification for law, and had been making a beginning with foreign law rather than with the main corpus of Anglo-American law.

Through the offices of the Council on Library Resources the needs of the American Association of Law Libraries were presented to the Library of Congress and a plan was agreed upon for giving some priority to work on those categories of material of most interest to American law libraries. To assist this potentially useful enterprise by

facilitating the discussions which are contemplated in the plan — in which the Library of Congress, the American Association of Law Libraries, the Association of American Law Schools and the American Law Institute will be represented — the Council made a small grant to the Library of Congress.

Support given by the Council on Library Resources to an earlier effort toward standardization in cataloging has resulted in publication by the American Library Association, during the summer of 1959, of *Cataloging of Persian Works, Including Rules for Transliteration, Entry and Description* (Bibliography, Item 13).* The author is Dr., Nasser Sharify, formerly Deputy Parliamentary Librarian of Iran and presently with Unesco in Paris as Program Assistant of the Library Development Section, Libraries Division.

*Cataloging
Persian
Works*

Selection, as has been mentioned, supplies the basic principle on which all devices for bibliographic access are founded, and the librarian's function is to anticipate his readers' needs and to make the most useful selection from the world's literature that his funds will permit. This is not an easy task. The quantities of individual titles to be considered, and the inadequacies of the services which must be depended upon for evaluation leading to selection are only two chief obstacles.

*A "New
Shaw"*

College libraries, and public libraries having similar book selection requirements, are particularly ill served in book-selection services. They must, with smaller budgets and much more limited resources in specialized knowledge, select from the same great total of publication as do universities with ample funds, staff, and access to expert advice. The work familiarly known as "Shaw"† provided college libraries with a useful basic list twenty years ago, but is of course out of date: it was not sup-

*References in this form are to Appendix B.

†Charles B. Shaw: *A List of Books for College Libraries* [prepared for the Carnegie Corporation of New York], 2d preliminary edition. Chicago: American Library Association, 1931. [*Supplement*], 1931-38. 1940.

ported by a continuous book-selection service. More recently, the *Lamont Library Catalogue** has served purposes similar to "Shaw", but is similarly obsolescent. Consequently, when the University of Michigan was making a selection of books for its new undergraduate library, opened at the beginning of 1959, it was compelled to make a new review of the world's literature for this purpose. The Michigan List, which is recorded on cards of which a photocopy may be obtained, must in its turn be brought up to date by the other institutions which wish to make use of it.

It would seem, in consequence, that here is an unmet need, basic to the operations of libraries, in which the Council might interest itself. But the matter offers certain difficulties. It is easy enough, perhaps, to prepare a "New Shaw," but how to keep it current? Both the basic volume and the continuing service would be expensive. Is the need such as to justify this expense and to assure self-support in whole or in part? Is a selection list of this kind desirable in any case, or does it tend to standardization and regimentation in the very area in which libraries should be freest from constraint?

To explore these questions the Council asked the American Library Association to sponsor a meeting, held in Chicago on April 20-21, 1959, in which were represented the college, university and public libraries which would be the users of such a book-selection service, and the publishers of existing book-selection services. The discussions were favorable to the establishment of a "New Shaw" on a continuing basis, and the Council has since pursued its explorations as to the manner in which this may be accomplished (Bibliography, Items 5, 6).

Automatic Indexing

Because the seeker for information never knows, at the commencement of his inquiry, what books or other book-like materials will eventually be found to contain the information he seeks, it is usual to provide clues based on the subject matter of the book. These clues are sometimes expressed in the symbols of a subject classification.

*Harvard University Library. *Lamont Library Catalogue*, prepared by Philip J. McNiff. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1953.

Other devices may be employed, too. Typically, however, they are conveyed through words. These words, variously called "subject headings," "index entries," or "descriptors," represent the cataloger's or indexer's judgment both as to the subject-content of the book and as to the verbal route by which an inquirer will seek information on that subject. It is unnecessary to underscore the importance of the subject-cataloger's or indexer's function.

This fact is reflected in the vast amount of subject cataloging and indexing which goes on every day. So exacting and so important is this activity that there are indexing operations carried on even in individual subjects by private professional groups which cost over a million dollars a year.

Meanwhile, the effect of the proliferation of publications has been to require an intensification of the minuteness of the analysis. The Alexandrine Library could adequately arrange the historical books under the simple heading "History;" a library must be small indeed which can still do this. *Chemical Abstracts*, when the literature of chemistry totaled fewer than ten thousand articles a year, could analyze effectively with 3.5 entries per article; now, when this literature approximates 100,000 articles a year, 12.5 index entries are needed per article, and individual articles have required more than a thousand entries. Humanistic studies have required indexes — concordances — which list every word in a text.

It consequently appears that the needs of intellectual work require ever-increasing analysis of more and more publications. The available man power for such analysis and the effectiveness of the vehicles for the results were never sufficient, and it seems unlikely that they ever become so. The situation brings to mind the problem of the telephone switchboard. If this had continued on a manual basis, there would not have been enough woman power to operate the boards. The only solution was through mechanization. It is by analogy not too early to explore the similar but more difficult problem of subject-analysis.

The question is, therefore, whether subject-analysis can be mechanized, whether machines can be devised which will recognize the meaning of words and supply the correct subject-entry to reflect that meaning. This problem is recognizably similar to that of machine translation; both involve the recognition of distinctions of meaning through techniques which can be mechanized. Whether or not a complete answer to this question is found, it may be expected that the very exploration of it may so improve our knowledge of the process of subject-analysis that it may derive improvement, either through modification of the procedures or of the channels through which the results are communicated.

Accordingly, the Council has placed a contract with Ramo-Wooldridge, a division of Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc., for an initial study of word correlation which will try to identify relations between words so as to suggest methods by which some parts or the whole of the process of subject-analysis may be accomplished mechanically. The project is under the direction of Don R. Swanson. Dr. Noam A. Chomsky, of the Institute for Advanced Study, and Dr. Paul Garvin, of Georgetown University, both professors of linguistics, are serving as consultants.

*International
Inventory of
Musical Sources*

The International Inventory of Musical Sources is sponsored by the International Musicological Society and the International Association of Music Libraries. American participation is under the auspices of the American Musicological Society and the Music Library Association. To enable the latter's representative, Richard S. Hill, of the Music Division, Library of Congress, to attend a policy meeting of the joint international committee in Basle in April 1959, the Council made a small grant. The inventory, which may be likened to a union catalog, will very likely run to a hundred published volumes. Nations in the Americas are participating with countries in Europe.

*The
"Cataloger's
Camera"*

In the preceding *Annual Report* was described a projected device for the production of catalog cards which would, by a dry process, reproduce the "unit entry" of a catalog card in multiple identical copies, and at the same

time transcribe upon individual cards as needed the distinguishing "added entries" under which these particular cards are to be filed. The Radio Corporation of America, with which a contract was placed for the construction of a working model of this machine, known as the "cataloger's camera," produced a device which can reproduce a catalog card in fourteen seconds. However, the thickness of the card —as contrasted with paper — created electrostatic conditions which resulted in an image not yet suitable for use in library catalogs. The machine has been left with the manufacturer for further development beyond the requirements of the contract. (Bibliography, Item 7).

PHYSICAL ACCESS

"As we do not live in an age of miracles, it is not to be doubted that Indian scholars will want the help of many books to qualify them to become good pastors and teachers." So in part read the instructions to John Randolph, Esquire, bound for England in 1732, from the President and Masters of the College of William and Mary. In a word, barring a miracle, it is not enough to know of a book's existence; to be useful, the book must be in hand. Only then is the process completed of which identification is but a preliminary step.

During the year just past, the Council assisted a number of projects intended to improve the means through which readers and the books they want are brought together in libraries. These projects may be categorized as follows:

Cooperative acquisition — furtherance of efforts for assuring the availability of books needed in research.

Prevention of deterioration of book-stock — demonstration of methods for manufacturing improved book-papers and for delaying deterioration of present book stock.

Studies of storage problems in large research libraries.

Experimental publication and distribution in micro-form.

Development of a system for high-density storage and rapid access through microphotography.

Development of devices for private use of microcopy.

Cooperative Acquisition

The Farmington Plan for the cooperative acquisition of foreign publications, as described in the Council's previous *Annual Report*, sprang from the World War II discovery that American research libraries were all purchasing from amongst the same group of "best" books and that, in consequence, many important though less than "best" books were not represented in any American collection. As a result, the Association of Research Libraries developed a cooperative effort, in which some sixty libraries participate, whereby each library assumes responsibility for securing all books of potential value for research in a particular field of study and to report its acquisitions to the National Union Catalog.

This Plan became effective for the books published in 1948. In the interest of success, it was limited in many respects: publications in non-Roman alphabets, serials, government documents and certain other categories were deliberately omitted from its scope. Even with its delimitations, the operation of the Plan has posed many difficulties.

The Council last year assisted the Association in a review of the effectiveness of the results of the experiment during its first decade, this review being intended to lay the basis for decisions whether the Plan should be continued or discontinued, extended, further limited, or modified in various details.

The review was conducted by Robert Vosper, Director, and Robert L. Talmadge, Associate Director of Libraries of the University of Kansas, under the supervision of the Association's Farmington Plan Committee, headed by Dr. Robert B. Downs, Director of Libraries, University of Illinois. The report (Bibliography, Item 2) was brought to a meeting of the participants in the Plan in Chicago in January 1959. There it was agreed to continue the Plan in spite of the impositions which it makes on individual libraries, to extend it to geographical and linguistic areas not now covered, to widen its scope to periodicals

and government publications if possible, and to work more closely than heretofore with scholarly groups having special interests in particular categories of material. To effect the last decision, seven subcommittees have been established with responsibility for the principal geographic-linguistic areas: Far East, Near East, Slavic, Western Europe, Southeast Asia, Africa and Latin America. Each of these subcommittees is to make arrangements with its counterparts in area and linguistic studies.

It is foreseen that this extension of the Plan will involve certain costs of bibliographical inquiry and preparation, including travel. The Council has made a new grant to enable the Association to pursue the extension of the Plan with utmost effectiveness.

One of the Council's first grants was to the Virginia State Library to undertake an inquiry into the extent and causes of the deterioration of paper in libraries, and to identify, if possible, methods of improvement. A report of this investigation, conducted by the well known document restorer, William J. Barrow, working with groups of librarians and paper chemists, appeared in the April 24, 1959, issue of *Science* under the title "Permanence in Book Papers" (Bibliography, Item 27). This report showed that while many book papers already 500 years or more old still have an expected life of many hundreds of years, the average American non-fiction book of the first decade of this century retains only 4% of the strength of a typical modern paper, and that the paper in the average American non-fiction publication of the 1940's has already lost 64% of what may be presumed to have been its original strength. The report also showed that the inexpensive incorporation of certain buffer salts during manufacture may be expected to extend the life expectancy of paper many times and that even paper already manufactured into books may be similarly treated.

Accordingly, the Council has made a new grant to the Virginia State Library to test the applicability of the proposed process by making experimental runs of paper and by testing and publishing the results, with the objective

*Preservation
of Book
Stock*

of finding a method for making a more durable, a more permanent paper than is now being used; a paper which will also be commercially practical. A further objective is to develop a standard of permanence-durability for books subject to prospective long or frequent use. A final objective is to develop, test and measure the costs of manual application of the preservation processes to existing books.

*Storage
Problems
of Large
Research
Libraries*

An effect of size of research libraries, previously mentioned, is that the channels of communication become clogged by the intermixture of the old and the new, the domestic and the foreign, the important and the trivial. Granted the necessity for maintaining all this material, yet the interest of most users demands routes to needed books which bypass the masses of material of little or no relevance and lead directly to the fewer books of greatest use. The interest of the librarian similarly requires that he devote his best space to the more used material. How to accomplish these objectives without introducing further confusions into the cataloging and shelving systems or without nullifying the usefulness of the material of lower demand, are problems which have not been satisfactorily solved. The principal available solution, off-campus compact storage, has provided only a partial and not very satisfactory answer.

In October 1958 the Council convened a meeting of librarians of large general research libraries to discuss these problems and to consider possible inquiries looking to the solutions (Bibliography, Items 34, 35). It was recognized that many devices are applicable to the problem: compact storage of various kinds, cooperative storage, miniaturization through microcopying, mechanization of book transport systems, telefacsimile, and the like. It was hoped that a manual, for the guidance of those encountering space problems resulting from exhaustion of storage space, might gradually be developed to reflect actual experience in terms of service and of costs of the various solutions. The Council was encouraged to support a number of specific studies in this area.

Subsequently, the Council made a grant to Yale University for a study of the bases for, and the results of, the university library's selective book retirement program. This program involves weeding of less-used books from the major collections and their retirement to compact storage. It is the purpose of the study to improve, in discussions with the faculty, the criteria for weeding, to ascertain what results this weeding has upon research and to explore the question of what compensations should be made for the reduced bibliographic and physical accessibility imposed. The study is being made by Lee Ash under the supervision of John H. Ottemiller, Associate University Librarian. The Council has similarly made a grant to the University of Chicago to study the arrangements which might be effected, in the interest of the best use of space, in a new library building. Again, the study involves close cooperation with the academic departments, and will also take into consideration records of actual use of the existing collection. The study is under the supervision of Herman H. Fussler, Director, The University Library.

Both of these studies may be expected to provide information of importance in the disposition of the space problems of research libraries.

Microcopying offers an attractive solution to the problems of storage resulting from size. The costs of microcopying are such, however, that the employment of this technique is rarely justified by space-saving alone. The microfilming of newspapers, for example, is undertaken not only for space-saving but also for preservation and to avoid costs of binding. In addition, for want of devices making the private use of microtext convenient, libraries have so far been unable to exploit microcopy in the same way that they do originals.

The Council's efforts toward the development of a device for convenient private use of microtext are described below. However, in making a grant to the American Institute of Biological Sciences to assist the publication of a scientific journal in microform, the Coun-

*Publication
in
Microform*

cil had other interests as well. It wished to encourage initial publication in this form, both in order to observe the effects on libraries and users and to avoid later necessity for microcopying. This journal, *Wildlife Disease*, the quarterly publication of the Wildlife Disease Association, is issued on 3 x 5 inch Microcards, each card containing up to forty-seven miniaturized pages. This is believed to be the first time that a learned journal had made its original appearance in microtext (Bibliography, Items 49-51). The photographic process involved has immediately recognizable advantages: it removes limitations upon the amount of tabular matter published; it permits greater veridicity than do other reproduction processes in publication of photographs. To enable the subscribers to read this journal, the Council provided the improved hand-reader described below. At the end of the third year of the project, which is supported jointly with the Council by the National Science Foundation, the Association will determine whether to continue to issue in microform or whether to resort to full scale publication.

*High
Density
Storage*

The possibilities of high-density storage of library materials through photographic techniques of reduction and enlargement have attracted many, but have never been effectively put to use. As a step in this direction, the Council has awarded a contract to the Avco Manufacturing Corporation (Crosley Division). The contract is for development at Avco's Electronics Research Laboratory, in Boston, of an experimental high-density direct-access photostorage and retrieval system for library materials. The work is under the direction of Louis H. Martin, Senior Staff Engineer, and is expected to take about a year. It is devoted specifically to development of the following:

1. A step-and-repeat camera suitable for preparing high-reduction microphotographic storage fields. The purpose is to demonstrate feasibility of conveniently preparing micro images from original books and other publications so faithfully that no detail observable by the naked eye in the original is wanting in the microcopy.

2. Direct-access photo-memory selection mechanisms to demonstrate the practicability of selecting information stored in microscopic form, and to demonstrate photographic and electronic reproduction of the content.

3. Electronic buffer storage facilities to demonstrate the feasibility of supplying information from the photo-memory simultaneously in electronic or optical form to a number of users.

Should the foregoing investigations be successful, other elements of the system to be developed include a searching system, a method for "printing out" hard copy that will be characterized by high definition and very faithful reproduction, and a method of transmission of the stored images to remote points, with "print out" — or "read out" — at these points.

It is not to be expected that these problems can be solved instantly. Nevertheless, were it for example possible to place the complete contents of all the periodicals indexed in the *Readers Guide to Periodical Literature* or in *Chemical Abstracts* in microstorage such as is here envisaged, conditions of storage, access and use might be greatly improved.

The private reader now constitutes the principal obstacle to exploitation of microtext in libraries. To read this microtext he must typically go to a special area of the library and use an elaborate, expensive and immovable device. He cannot conveniently read such text in microcopy at home, on the street car, or in bed. Could his reading of microcopy be made as convenient as of the original it might well have a significant effect on reading habits and library practices.

Accordingly, the Council placed a contract with the Microcard Corporation for the improvement of its hand reader for micro opaques — either through reduction in cost of the existing devices or through the improvement of its optical characteristics. It was found possible to convert this reader for use with ambient light instead of with lighting equipment, and thus to reduce the cost

*Hand Readers
for Micro
Opaques*

materially. At this point the Council was almost prepared to make arrangements for the manufacture of the improved device, and indeed supplied copies in an intermediate form for use in the Wildlife Disease project. Before arranging for such manufacture, however, it seemed worth while to attempt further to improve the optics. The Council has therefore placed a contract with the John R. Miles Company to design such a lens.

The Council, in another action in the field of private use of microtext, has made a grant to Dr. Vernon D. Tate, the librarian of the United States Naval Academy, who is one of those having the longest interest in the applications of microcopy to library and archival work. The contract is for development of a device for converting roll microfilm into flat film (microfiches).

Dissemination of Information

Microfilming is an accepted technique of the business and engineering world, where staff can be assigned to the continuous operation of the mechanisms specifically designed for the work. Library use of microcopy differs from this; users are not paid to sit at a console; their use of microcopy is sporadic and they wish to be free to use it anywhere, especially where they are already working with full scale materials.

Thirty years ago, when microfilm was first introduced both to business and library uses, there was little reading equipment; now, by contrast, hundreds of differing machines are available, most of which are designed for commercial use. It is difficult for librarians to ascertain the comparative merits of machines for their particular purposes. An attempt to supply this deficiency has been made by the *Manual on Documentary Reproduction and Selection*, published by the International Federation for Documentation in The Hague. But this is a three-volume loose-leaf service, covering the world market and containing extended descriptions which do not permit easy comparison of particular devices.

In May 1958 the Council convoked a meeting to explore next steps in the study of the problems of micro-

forms in libraries. Among the recommendations of the group were that action should be taken to disseminate information among librarians regarding available microfilm equipment and techniques. Accordingly, the Council made a grant to the National Microfilm Association to be used in connection with its meeting in Washington, April 2-4, 1959. Several undertakings were involved. The first was the publication of a *Guide to Microreproduction Equipment*, prepared by Hubbard W. Ballou, Head of Photographic Service, Columbia University Library (Bibliography, Item 47). This 438-page *Guide*, complete with illustrations, lists equipment available for purchase in the United States and provides in standard form data regarding capacity, performance and price for each item. Copies of this work were made available to the registrants at the meeting and, as long as the edition lasted, to requesting libraries. The Association has since reprinted the work for sale.

Other undertakings were the assemblage of an historical exhibit, including the original camera used by René Prudent Patrice Dagron, one of the fathers of microfilm, for preparing the microcopies used in the pigeon post during the siege of Paris, 1870-71. Finally, the Council enabled the Association to assist in paying the expense of travel to the Conference by persons having responsibilities for microcopying in research libraries, and the program was developed with a view to the interest of these persons.

The dependence of research on copying needs no emphasis; it can probably be truly stated that research did not begin until methods of copying made possible the bringing together of data from various sources. The Library of Congress produces some 14,000,000 photocopies (pages) per year; the University of California Library's photographic laboratory did nearly a half million dollars worth of business in its first decade, just completed. But photographic copying as usually practiced involves delays for laboratory processing which it would be desirable, for many purposes, to obviate.

*Copying in
Libraries*

The Council has placed a contract with Eugene Garfield Associates for the development of a working model of the "Copywriter," a device intended to facilitate the copying of short passages, bibliographic entries and extracts. The principle is that of the scanning pencil.

The Council also placed a contract during the year with Dr. Lyman Chalkley, the inventor of dye cyanides, for a sensitometric study to ascertain the applicability of these, as compared with other photosensitive materials, to copying devices requiring no laboratory processing. Dr. Chalkley's results have been published under the title, "Conditions for Projection Copying on Dye Cyanide Sensitized Materials" (Bibliography, Item 54), and the Council is seeking occasion to apply the findings.

*Legal
Problems of
Photocopying*

From the foregoing paragraphs it will appear that many of the projects in which the Council has interested and will undoubtedly continue to interest itself, involve methods of copying. This is as it should be; libraries owe their existence in the very first place to the ability to copy. But library copying often involves legal considerations. To explore especially those related to copyright, the Council has made a grant to the Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying, of which Edward G. Freehafer, Director of the New York Public Library, is chairman. The committee represents the American Library Association, American Association of Law Libraries, the Association of Research Libraries and the Special Libraries Association. To assist in these studies the Committee has obtained the services of the law firm Webster, Sheffield and Chrystie.

ADMINISTRATIVE FACTORS

The Council's previous *Annual Report* reviewed the considerations which demonstrate the need of a program of testing and standardization specifically applied to the uses of library work. It described a study then in progress, under the auspices of the American Library Association

with the support of the Council, in the course of which John H. Ottemiller, Associate Librarian of Yale University, was attempting to ascertain whether such a program might be devised.

Mr. Ottemiller's report became available in the fall of 1958 (Bibliography, Item 58), and was reviewed by the American Library Association's Library Administration Division, which has responsibilities relating to equipment, supplies, buildings, and systems. As a result, the Association proposed to the Council a three-year program in this field. A grant made for the purpose in December, 1958, makes it possible for the Association to establish an office entitled the "Library Technology Project," of which Frazer G. Poole, formerly assistant librarian of Santa Barbara College, has been appointed director (Bibliography, Item 57). The first objective of the project will be to accumulate the extensive existing information on standards and testing applicable to library uses; at a later point it will provide an information service on the information so accumulated. It will simultaneously conduct an educational campaign among librarians on the matters involved, plan specific projects of testing, standardization and research, and explore the methods for continuing the operation on a self-supporting basis.

The term "National Library" has possessed little meaning beyond indicating that an institution to which it is applied is a principal library owned by a national government. Many such libraries are renowned especially for their valuable collections. In the United States the term has received an additional endowment of meaning because of the important assistance rendered by its principal national libraries in the daily work of the other libraries of the country.

This situation has been emulated in other countries. Recently, in the interest of promoting the central services of national libraries, Unesco arranged for a Symposium on National Libraries in Europe, held in Vienna in September, 1958. Although the scope of the meeting was limited to Europe, national librarians from other countries

*Services of
National
Libraries*

were invited. It seemed important to the Council that the United States be represented, and a small grant to the Library of Congress made this possible (Bibliography, Item 33).

*National
Library
Week, 1959*

Again, as in the preceding year, the Council made a grant in support of National Library Week. The results of the previous (first) observance appeared fully to justify the project in terms of the increased use and support of libraries which were stimulated by it throughout the country (Bibliography, Items 39, 40).

FACT FINDING AND PLANNING FOR RESEARCH

*Study of
Federal
Libraries*

The Federal Government of the United States is undoubtedly the outstanding owner and operator of libraries in the world. It maintains some 125 libraries — the largest with a collection of more than thirty-three million pieces — in the District of Columbia alone; its libraries of medicine and agriculture are outstanding; it maintains six or more libraries of college-university rank, and it operates many thousands of libraries throughout the country — and indeed the world — ranging in character from small recreational collections in isolated outposts to extensive special libraries in the fine arts, nuclear physics, forest products, and other subject areas.

These libraries in every case owe their establishment and maintenance to the needs of a governmental activity. Yet, in sum, they constitute an invaluable national resource. This fact has been acknowledged by Federal statute and many of the libraries provide public services under its authorization. Nevertheless, the fact remains that each library works directly within the confines of the agency in which it is embodied. There are no formalized relations between them and few between them and the library users of the country.

This situation results in substantial losses — many actual and even more potential. Proposals for introducing a measure of system have been made regularly at least since Melvil Dewey proposed it to the Congressional Joint Committee on the Library in 1896. But the basis in fact finding and planning for such improvement, although sought on several occasions — *e.g.*, in the David S. Hill, Carleton B. Joeckel and Library of Congress Planning Committee reports of 1936, 1938 and 1947 — has been hitherto insufficient.

The prospective application of information-storage and communication devices such as electronic memories, teletype and telefacsimile, to library work, and the belief that such devices might profitably be employed among the Federal libraries, have led to a renewal of the proposals. An informal committee, representing the principal library groups in the District of Columbia (and in one case — the Special Libraries Association — the national organization), proposed to the Council an inquiry into the entire basis of establishment, operation, staffing, services and the intra and inter-agency and public relations of the Federal libraries.

The Council has adopted this proposal. The Brookings Institution, perceiving in this question an opportunity for pursuing its interest in government relations, has undertaken as a result an 18-month study under the direction of one of its senior staff members, Dr. Charles A. H. Thomson. As the consultant for this study the Institution has enlisted the assistance of Dr. Luther H. Evans, formerly Librarian of Congress and more recently Director General of Unesco.* The study will emphasize the departmental — *i.e.*, District of Columbia — libraries of the Executive Branch of the Federal Government. The libraries of the Legislative and Judicial Branches, and the educational and non-departmental libraries will be examined only to the extent that is needed to ascertain interrelationships.

*Dr. Evans succeeded Dr. Thomson as project director, and was also named a senior staff member, upon the latter's resignation in October 1959.

*Study of the
Independent
Historical
Societies*

Historical studies in the United States owe much to the privately supported historical societies of the Eastern seaboard — such organizations as the Massachusetts Historical Society (1798), American Antiquarian Society (1812), Historical Society of Pennsylvania (1824), and Virginia Historical Society (1884). These and similar groups led in preserving the source materials for American history, in assembling research collections and in programs of historical publication. As evidence of the recognition of the importance of the role which they have played, it is noteworthy that, as our population has moved westward, historical societies have been taken under the protection of the State governments and west of the Appalachians are for the most part constituted as governmental or quasi-governmental agencies.

Meanwhile, however, the resources of the privately supported societies have diminished in comparative terms, and they find that they are unable to execute effectively the responsibilities which their important collections of research materials require of them.

The Council has accordingly given support to a survey of the situation to be conducted by Walter Muir Whitehill, the librarian of the Boston Athenaeum, and sponsored by the four societies mentioned above. This two-year inquiry will attempt to describe the role of these organizations, provide a basis for closer collaboration among them, and suggest methods for strengthening their support and their effectiveness. The study is to result in publication, prospectively during 1960.

*National
Bureau of
Standards
Clearing House
on Information
Processing
Systems*

The recognition that “data processing” is but one aspect of the series of operations with which libraries are concerned has been slow in developing. Initially, “data processing” was thought of as the manipulation — with mechanical or electronic devices whenever possible — of “alpha-numeric” data — *i.e.*, words and figures — such as might be involved in payroll and other accounting systems. Gradually the understanding has developed that the ma-

nipulation of such data is common to all intellectual work. "Information storage and retrieval," "machine translation," "machine indexing," "automatic-abstracting," and the preparation of concordances by mechanical means are all examples of the extension of "data processing" into operations in which libraries have an interest.

The International Conference on Scientific Information, to which the Council gave support, met in Washington November 16-21, 1958. It brought together several hundreds of persons, from all parts of the world, possessing the diverse backgrounds of mathematicians, engineers, physicists, chemists, linguists, logicians, librarians and documentalists. At this meeting, if not before, a realization was achieved of the common concern in "data processing" on the part of all the disciplines involved, and of its importance in connection with the storage, organization and communication of information in all affairs of life — and significantly in research (Bibliography, Item 56).

Consequently, much developmental work is now being pursued in this area by representatives of many interests, governmental, academic, industrial and commercial. The National Bureau of Standards has established a Data Processing Systems Division, of which Dr. Samuel N. Alexander is Chief. The National Science Foundation has asked the Bureau to establish a service intended to assist in the coordination of work. Accordingly, under an arrangement which the Council has co-sponsored with the Foundation, the Division has established a service of which the first phase is to collect information on "information processing systems," to provide a clearing house service on this material, to prepare reviews of the state of the art, and to test and compare techniques. It is expected that this service will be of great use to those organizations, among others, which like the Foundation and the Council have an interest in research in this field but which require much more precise information about activity in it than is now readily available.

*First
Assembly
of State
Librarians*

The libraries of the state governments of the United States have possessed very unequal status with respect to library work within their areas. Some have long possessed state-wide functions; others have been merely small libraries serving the state legislatures. In recent years there have been marked developments in this situation, springing from the increasing awareness that good library service must be based upon larger units of use and support than has for the most part been the rule, and that the availability of services from a central agency is a factor important for efficiency. A culminating circumstance has been the Federal Library Services Act of 1956 which has generally caused an increase in the state-wide responsibilities of the state libraries.

This rapidly changing situation has called for deliberate recognition and evaluation. A meeting for this purpose, held in Washington in November 1958 as the First Assembly of State Librarians was very naturally sponsored by the Library of Congress which had long cultivated relations with the state libraries, and which has been the leader in providing central services to other libraries. To assist in making the work of this First Assembly most profitable by facilitating arrangements for speakers and meetings, the Council made a small grant for which the late Alton H. Keller, who had been the most active member of the Library of Congress staff in developing these federal-state relationships, served as financial officer. The grant was used with the anticipated results (Bibliography, Item 36). Mr. Keller's untimely death did not permit him to report on the disbursements, however, and this duty fell to his alternate, Ralph Hudson, Oklahoma State Librarian.

*Library
Schools
Committee
on Research*

The Federal Library Services Act has also emphasized the need for research in the problems of public libraries. Dean Robert D. Leigh of the School of Library Service, Columbia University, formerly director of the Public Library Survey, 1947-50, has formed a Library Schools Committee on Research on Inter-Library Cooperation.

Its objective is, with joint planning, to insure the most effective employment of the meager resources for research in this area available to those of the country's library schools which support Ph.D. programs. The Council has made a small grant to aid the committee in its work.

Early in 1958 the Council made a small grant to the American Library Association for a technical and economic evaluation of the experience of the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc. This organization, established with Council support in 1957, is a cooperative enterprise on the part of a number of small and medium size libraries, separated by distances of up to two hundred and fifty miles, for providing centralized book processing services. The study was conducted by Mrs. Brigitte L. Kenney, a student at the Graduate Library School, University of Chicago, working under the direction of Professors Leon Carnovsky and Ruth French Strout in cooperation with Mrs. Orcena Mahoney, the Executive Secretary of the Resources and Technical Services Division of the American Library Association. Mrs. Kenney's study, *Centralized Processing, A Report of the Establishment and First Year of Operation of the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.* (Bibliography, Item 23), has been published by the Association, thus placing the experience gained at the disposal of the library world generally.

*Cooperative
Centralized
Processing
of Books*

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Accountant's Opinion

AUGUST 7, 1959

TO THE BOARD OF DIRECTORS OF
COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc., at June 30, 1959 and the expenditures and income for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of such statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards, and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other procedures as we considered necessary.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

JUNE 30, 1959

ASSETS

Cash	\$ 301,553
Investments, at cost (approximate market):	
U. S. Treasury Bills, due August 1959	397,088
U. S. Treasury Notes, 3¼% due May 1960	497,656
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation (collectible \$1,250,000 annually to June 30, 1961)	2,500,000
Accrued interest receivable and deposits	3,613
	<u>\$3,699,910</u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and research contracts payable, per accompanying statement	\$ 811,277
Accounts payable and accrued salaries	4,210
Fund balance:	
Balance June 30, 1958	\$4,238,955
Expenditures less income for the year	<u>1,354,532</u> <u>2,884,423</u>
	<u>\$3,699,910</u>

STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1959

EXPENDITURES

Grants, contracts and Council-administered projects	\$1,275,822	
Less adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded	17,673	\$1,258,149
General administrative expense —		
Compensation and employee benefits	90,634	
Rent	6,300	
Professional services	4,656	
Furniture and equipment	670	
Travel and meetings	9,737	
Supplies, printing, insurance, communications and other	11,250	123,247
		\$1,381,396

INCOME

From investments		26,864
Expenditures less income		\$1,354,532
		\$1,354,532

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1959

	Payable June 30 1958	Grant, contract or project	Adjust- ments	Pay- ments (Net)	Payable June 30 1959
American Historical Association					
Compilation of The Guide to Photocopied Historical Material in the United States and Canada	\$ 28,000	\$ 2,420		\$ 30,420	
American Institute of Biological Sciences					
For the experimental publication of a scientific journal in microform		11,274		6,274	\$ 5,000
American Library Association					
Analysis and report of the Southwest Missouri Library Service Cooperative Processing Center			\$ 206	(206)	
"Library Technology" — a feasibility study ..			2,262	(2,262)	
"Library Technology" — a program of testing and standardization of library equipment, supplies and systems		136,395		35,000	101,395
Travel grants to promote the international coordination of cataloging rules			1,173	(1,173)	
AVCO Manufacturing Corporation (Crosley Division)					
Development of an experimental high-density direct-access photostorage and retrieval system for library materials		201,531		83,678	117,853
Boston Athenaeum (on behalf of four independent historical societies)					
Study of the independent historical societies .		20,000		20,000	
Brookings Institution					
For a survey of Federal Government libraries .		72,965		37,987	34,978
Lyman Chalkley					
To investigate photographic speed of dye cyanides and other dry-process photosensitive materials		2,000		2,000	
Columbia University, on behalf of the Library Schools Committee on Research on Interlibrary Cooperation					
To aid in the planning of research by the Committee		5,610		5,610	
Committee on a Survey of Library Education of the Joint Committee on Library Education of the Council of National Library Associations					
For a meeting of the Committee	1,000		438	562	
The de Florez Company, Inc.					
Design plan for an automatic book-cradle/page-turner	5,000			5,000	

	Payable June 30 1958	Grant, contract or project	Adjust- ments	Pay- ments (Net)	Payable June 30 1959
Eugene Garfield Associates Development of experimental model of the "Copywriter"		\$ 9,100		\$ 1,000	\$ 8,100
Harvard College (on behalf of the Committee on Slavic and East European Studies of the Association of Research Libraries) Publication of Russian and East European Pub- lications in American Libraries		2,940		2,940	
International Federation of Library Associations For a preliminary meeting on the international coordination of cataloging rules	\$ 19,995			19,995	
Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials, Inc. For a meeting of the Committee		750		750	
Assistance toward placing the record of serials in libraries in the United States and Canada on a continuing basis (3rd Edition of the Union List of Serials , etc.)		244,651			244,651
Alton H. Keller Toward the expenses of the first Assembly of State Librarians		400		400	
Harry J. Krould A study of the regional coordination of library reference services	4,600	1,200	\$ 285	5,515	
Library of Congress Assistance toward the development of a shelf- classification for law books		4,500		4,500	
Creation of a national union catalog of manu- script collections		200,000		100,000	100,000
For travel expenses in connection with the par- ticipation by the Librarian of Congress in the Symposium on National Libraries in Europe		3,000		3,000	
Meeting to explore problems connected with book-selection in college libraries*		7,216	2,971	4,245	
Meeting to plan studies toward the solution of the space problems of large (general) research libraries*		2,000	235	1,765	
The Microcard Corporation Prototypes of hand reading devices for micro- opaques	5,750	765		6,515	

	Payable June 30 1958	Grant, contract or project	Adjust- ments	Pay- ments (Net)	Payable June 30 1959
Development of a head-supported reader for micro-opaques		\$ 3,500			\$ 3,500
John R. Miles Company					
Preliminary investigation toward designing a 20x magnifier for reading micro-opaques ..		500	\$ 1	\$ 499	
For development of a 20x magnifier for reading micro-opaques		18,466		16,466	2,000
Music Library Association					
To assist United States participation in work on the international inventory of musical sources		538		538	
National Book Committee					
Assistance toward the expenses of National Library Week 1959		10,000		10,000	
National Library of Medicine					
Improvement of bibliographic compilation through mechanization with specific application to the Current List of Medical Literature	\$ 26,500			26,500	
National Microfilm Association					
Demonstration of microcopying techniques, equipment and applications		15,000		15,000	
National Science Foundation					
Toward support of the National Bureau of Standards Cooperative Research Advisory Service on Information Processing Systems, Phase I		20,000		20,000	
New York Public Library (on behalf of the Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying)					
For studies of legal problems involved in the photocopying of copyright material in libraries		4,000		4,000	
Dissemination of information resulting from the Virginia State Library's investigation of the deterioration of book stock*		1,600	2	1,598	
Princeton University (on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries)					
Survey and evaluation of the Farmington Plan			8,600	(8,600)	
Extension of the Farmington Plan for the Co-operative Acquisition of Foreign Publications		15,000		8,600	6,400
Radio Corporation of America					
Design plan for an automatic book-cradle/page-turner	5,000			5,000	

	Payable June 30 1958	Grant, contract or project	Adjust- ments	Pay- ments (Net)	Payable June 30 1959
Feasibility model of an electrofax card copier ("Cataloger's Camera")	\$ 22,789			\$ 22,789	
Rutgers University, Graduate School of Library Service					
Targets for research in library work	37,500			37,500	
Nasser Sharify					
Publication of a code for the cataloging of Persian materials		\$ 3,612		2,875	\$ 737
Vernon D. Tate					
Investigation of sheet microfilm		3,000		3,000	
Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc. (Ramo-Wooldridge Division)					
Studies in word correlation and automatic indexing		68,216			68,216
University of Chicago					
Study of patterns in the use of research library materials		84,600		40,000	44,600
University of Michigan					
Feasibility Study of "Telereference"	6,703	923		7,563	63
University of Virginia					
Closed circuit TV in a decentralized library situation			\$ 1,500	(1,500)	
Virginia State Library					
Improvement of permanence and durability of book papers		42,050		21,050	21,000
Sergius Yakobson, Boris I. Gorokhoff and Paul L. Horecky					
Preparation of a report on libraries in the information-dissemination process in the Soviet Union	4,750			4,750	
Toward expenses of publication of Libraries and Bibliographic Centers in the Soviet Union by Paul L. Horecky*		3,050		1,446	1,604
Toward expenses of publication of Publishing in the USSR by Boris I. Gorokhoff*		3,050		1,870	1,180
Yale University					
Development and demonstration of the basis, operation and results of the Yale University Library's Selective Book Retirement Program		50,000			50,000
Totals	\$167,587	\$1,275,822	\$17,673	\$614,459	\$811,277

*Council-administered project

APPENDIX A

PROGRAM POLICY OF THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

In the processes of communication by which knowledge and ideas are conveyed from one human mind to another past barriers even of space and time, libraries have through the centuries played an essential and noble part. But increasingly in our day, conventional library techniques are found unable to cope with the vast multiplication of the records in which knowledge and ideas are stored and conveyed. With present procedures, libraries in isolation are increasingly unable to state what recorded knowledge exists on a particular topic, or to make the relevant record available with sufficient promptness.

Meanwhile, however, a wide variety of new procedures and technical aids have emerged, offering promise of assistance toward the solution of library problems—through the improved organization of library services, particularly by interlibrary planning and collaboration; through techniques for storage of information in more condensed form and its transmission at increased rates of speed; and through statistical approaches which look not for unattainable perfection but for maximum service to the greatest number.

It seems clear that this is a good time through study and experiment to reexamine the total role of the library as a major link in the communication chain between mind and mind. Such a reexamination would inevitably look to the long-range, larger and more modern role of the library but it would not neglect the immediate practicalities required by existing library procedures. Nor would it disregard the fact that libraries mean many

things to many men — that one inquirer needs rapid access to minute particles of knowledge, while another must examine in detail, and from many aspects, large quantities of material relating to a topic of research.

Accordingly —

1. The purpose of the Council on Library Resources is to improve methods of acquiring, storing, organizing, retrieving, reproducing, and transmitting information in libraries. (For example, the whole series of problems created by serial publication needs particular attention.)

2. Improvement must be sought:

- a. by increasing the effectiveness of the conventional techniques employed in the operation of libraries;
- b. through application, within the framework of existing library techniques, of new concepts and of new technology, now available or to become available;
- c. through investigation of the potentialities possessed by newly developed knowledge, ideas and methods, including technology, for attaining the Council's objectives.

(For example, not only should the obvious applications of microphotography, machine storage, retrieval and reproduction, rapid pictorial transmission and the like be studied and improved, but the possibilities of systematic logical analysis to improve classification should be investigated and methods of rationalizing library organization should be explored.)

3. The Council, acting on its own behalf, and also through competent agencies already established and to be established, will seek to identify the critical problems and will make the necessary studies for attacking them.

4. If it is discovered that a potential exists, planning shall follow, conducted in such a way that the segments of the field are considered in relation to the whole.

(Planning may be conducted by the Council, by groups set up by it, or by recipients of grants.)

If a development appears feasible, economically, technically, and in terms of acceptability to the users of libraries, and a plan is formulated, it shall be implemented either in whole or in such parts as can be handled.

If it is not feasible, a mere statement that such a plan cannot be implemented until specified developments are achieved may serve a useful purpose.

5. The Council may vote to implement recommendations through grants.

- a. Long and short term programs shall be based on plans so formed. (For example, a long-term program might be a study of the application of computing machinery to storage, organization and retrieval of information. A short-term program might consist in an effort to improve and standardize microphotography and to produce an adequate inexpensive portable reader. Achievement of the long-term plan might render the short-term partly obsolete, but the utility of the latter would be so great that it should nevertheless be accomplished.)
- b. The Council will make grants from time to time to improve procedures of conventional library techniques if the proposals are of importance and general applicability. (For example, new methods of preparing and printing bibliographies.)
- c. Such proposals, as well as those whose purpose is to apply new ideas and technology within existing procedures of library work, will be given favorable consideration if they show promise of future development and general applications.

- d. Grants and contracts may be awarded to applicants whose proposals fall within the framework of the Council's plans and purposes, to contractors and others, and to agencies created by the Council for such purposes.
- e. The Council will confine its grants within the general framework here stated unless it discovers a new idea which is of such importance as to justify an exception. Worthy proposals outside the scope of the Council's activities may be referred by the President or the Directors to other foundations or benefactors with the official recommendation of the Council.

APPENDIX B

REPORTS OF PROJECTS AND PUBLICATIONS RESULTING FROM PROJECTS

Acquisition

Cooperative: The Farmington Plan

1. "ARL Meeting [on the Farmington Plan, January 26, 1959]". *College and Research Libraries* 20:156-157, March 1959.
2. Association of Research Libraries: *Farmington Plan Survey, Directed by Robert Vosper & Robert Talmadge, University of Kansas Libraries. Final Report, Presented at the Annual Meeting of ARL, Chicago January 2, 1959.* [Lawrence, Kansas, 1958.] Various pagination: [11] pp., printed; [308] 1., processed.
3. Talmadge, Robert L.: "The Farmington Plan Survey; an Interim Report". *College and Research Libraries* 19:375-383, September 1958.

Exchanges: The United States Book Exchange, Inc.

4. Williams, Edwin E.: *A Serviceable Reservoir; Report of a Survey of the United States Book Exchange.* Washington: The United States Book Exchange, Inc., 1959. 81 pp.

Book-Selection for College Libraries

5. *Meeting to Explore Some Current and Anticipated Problems in the Building of Book Collections in College Libraries, Edgewater Beach Hotel, Chicago, Illinois, April 20-21, 1959.* [Washington: Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1959] 10.1., processed.
6. "Report on Conference". *Library Journal*, 84:1765-1767. June 1, 1959. (Report on the meeting of April 20-21, 1959.)

Cataloging

"Cataloger's Camera"

7. Radio Corporation of America. Development Engineering Marketing, Defense Electronic Products: *Final Report. Automatic Enlarging Instant Copy Camera, April 6, 1959.* [Camden: The Corporation, 1959] 6 1., 4 pl., processed.

"Cataloging in Source"

8. Osborn, Andrew D.: *Cataloging at the Source; an Opportunity for Cooperation Between the Four Major Book Arts.* Chicago: American Library Association, 1958. 18 1., typescript.

9. U. S. Library of Congress. Processing Department: "Cataloging in Source." *Cataloging Service*. 48:1-3, September 1958; 50:1-4, November 1958; 53:1-17, June 1959.

International Coordination of Cataloging Rules

10. International Federation of Library Associations. International Cataloging Conference: *Bulletin*, 1 London: IFLA Working Group on Co-ordination of Cataloguing Principles, November 1958. Irregular, processed.

11. Osborn, Andrew D.: "At a German Library Association Conference." *ALA Bulletin*, 51: 773-5. November, 1957. [Account of the meeting of the German Library Association (Verein Deutscher Bibliothekare) in Lübeck in June 1957 by the American Library Association's representative.]

12. — —: "Zur Revision der Instruktionen für die Katalogisierung an Amerikanischen Bibliotheken; Vortrag, Gehalten auf dem Bibliothekartag in Lübeck am 13 Juni 1957. (Gekürzt)" *Zeitschrift für Bibliothekswesen und Bibliographie* 4:241-246, 1957.

Persian Works

13. Sharify, Nasser: *Cataloging of Persian Works, Including Rules for Transliteration, Entry and Description*. Chicago: American Library Association, 1959. xiv, 161 pp.

Closed-Circuit TV in a Decentralized Library Situation

14. Bristol, Roger: *Card Turner Problems: A Preliminary Investigation of the Feasibility of Long-Distance Consultation of Card Catalogs*. Charlottesville: Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 12 l., processed.

15. — —: "Closed-Circuit Television Experiment in a University Library." *Southeastern Librarian* 8:11-14, Spring, 1958.

16. — —: *Closed-Circuit TV Equipment as Used in a Decentralized Library Situation*. Charlottesville: Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 13 l., processed.

17. — —: *Microcard Images Transmitted by Closed-Circuit TV*. Charlottesville: Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 6 l., processed.

18. — —: *Page Turners: A Report of Their Usefulness for a Closed-Circuit TV Project*. Charlottesville: Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 14 l., processed.

19. Gibson, Frank Kenneth: *Closed-Circuit TV at the University of Virginia: A Summary Report*. Charlottesville: Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1959. 7 l., processed.

20. University of Virginia. Bureau of Public Administration: *A Report on an Experiment Involving the Use of Closed-Circuit TV in a Decentralized Library Situation*. [Charlottesville] The Bureau, 1958. v, 31 l., pl., processed.

Cooperative Centralized Processing of Books

21. Dennis, Willard K.: "Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.," *Missouri Library Association Quarterly*, 18:119-123. December, 1957.

22. Kenney, Brigitte L.: "Centralized Processing — Missouri Style," *Library Resources and Technical Services*, 2:185-198. Summer, 1958.

23. — —: *Cooperative Centralized Processing, A Report of the Establishment and First Year of Operation of the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.* Chicago, American Library Association, 1959. 98 pp.

24. Mahoney, Orcena: "An Experiment in Cooperative Processing," *ALA Bulletin*, 52:127-130. February, 1958.

Deterioration of Book-Stock — Causes and Remedies

25. Barrow, William J.: *Physical Strength of Non-Fiction Book Papers, 1900-1949. A Preliminary Report, December 1, 1957*. [Richmond, 1957] [35] l., processed.

26. — —: *Stabilization of Modern Book Papers. A Progress Report, June 1, 1958*. [Richmond, 1958] 10 l., processed.

27. Barrow, W. J., and Reavis C. Sproull: "Permanence in Book Papers," *Science*, 129:1075-1084, April 24, 1959.

28. Church, Randolph W.: "Is There a Doctor in the House?," *Publishers' Weekly*, 175: 76, 78-80, January 5, 1959.

29. — —: "Perish the Paper, Perish the Book, Perish the Thought: An Inquiry," *Publishers' Weekly*, 172: 54-58, September 2, 1957.

International Organization of Effort

30. Carter, Edward: *International Organization in Librarianship and Documentation*. [Washington, 1958] 59 l., processed.

Libraries

Coordination of Reference Services

31. Krould, Harry J.: *An Inquiry on Aspects of Public Library Reference Service*. [Washington, 1958.] 2 v., typescript.

In the Soviet Union

32. Horecky, Paul L.: *Libraries and Bibliographic Centers in the Soviet Union*. [Bloomington: Indiana University Publications, c 1959.] xviii, 287 pp.

National

33. [Mumford, L. Quincy:] "Report from the Librarian of Congress [on the Seminar on National Libraries in Europe, Vienna, Sept. 1958]" *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 17:611-612, October 27, 1958.

Space Problems

34. *Meeting to Plan Studies Toward the Solution of the Space Problems of Large (General) Research Libraries, Cosmos Club, Washington, D. C., October 27-28, 1958*. Washington: Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1958. 8 p. 1., processed. ("Corrigenda," 1 1.)

35. "Space Problems of Large (General) Research Libraries: Report of a Meeting," *College and Research Libraries* 20:217-220, May 1959.

State Libraries

36. *Assembly of State Librarians: Summary Proceedings of the Assembly of State Librarians held at the Library of Congress, November 12-14, 1958*. Washington: Library of Congress, 1959. v., 45 pp., processed.

Use and Support

37. Gaver, Mary Virginia: *Every Child Needs a School Library*. [Chicago: American Library Association, 1958.] 16 pp.

38. Ludington, Flora B.: *Books and Libraries — Tools of the Academic World*. [Chicago: American Library Association, 1958.] 15 pp.

39. National Book Committee, Inc.: *Report on the First Observance of National Library Week. Recognition and Response*. [New York: The Committee, 1958.] 16 pp.

40. — —: *1959 National Library Week. 2nd Annual Report*. [New York: The Committee, 1959.] [22] pp.

41. Parsons, Arthur H. Jr.: *Fountains, Not Reservoirs — The Public Library*. [Chicago: American Library Association, 1958.] 16 pp.

Long-Distance Consultation of Card Catalogs ("Telereference")

42. University of Michigan. Engineering Research Institute: *Final Report: Application of a Telereference System to Divisional Library Card Catalogs; A Feasibility Analysis*. [Ann Arbor: The Institute. For] Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1958. 91 pp.

Manuscripts

43. "National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections," *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 18: 347-349, June 22, 1959.

Mechanization of Bibliographical Compilation and Publication

44. "New Index Medicus." *National Library of Medicine News* 14: 1-3, August, 1959.
45. Taine, Seymour I.: "New Program for Indexing at the National Library of Medicine," *Bulletin of the Medical Library Association* 47:117-123. April, 1959.
46. U. S. National Library of Medicine: *Improvement of Bibliographic Compilation Through Mechanization as Applied to the Current List of Medical Literature. Interim Progress Report for Period Ending December 31, 1958 [May 31, 1959]*. Washington: The Library [1959], 2 v., processed.

Microcopy

Equipment

47. Ballou, Hubbard W.: *Guide to Microreproduction Equipment*. Annapolis, National Microfilm Association, 1959. viii, 438 pp.

In Libraries

48. *Meeting on the Problems of Microform in Libraries, Cosmos Club, Washington, D. C., May 23, 1958; Summary of Discussions*. Washington: Council on Library Resources, Inc. [1958]. 12 1., processed.

Journal Publication

49. Herman, Carlton M.: "New Journal in Microform," *A.I.B.S. [American Institute of Biological Sciences] Bulletin*, 9: 31-33, January, 1959.
50. "Proposed Journal Becomes an Actuality." *Wildlife Disease Association Newsletter* 19: 1-4, November, 1958.
51. *Wildlife Disease* no. 1 — [Washington: Wildlife Disease Association] January 1959. Quarterly; issued on Microcards with accompanying leaflet, *Abstracts from Wildlife Disease*.

Page-Turning Mechanisms

52. The de Florez Company, Inc.; *Report on Design Study of a Book-Cradle/Page-Turner*. Englewood Cliffs, N. J.: The Company, 1959. 18 1., 5 p1., processed.
53. Radio Corporation of America. Development Engineering, Defense Electronic Products: *Design Plan for the*

Development of an Automatic Page Turner by Elbert Marsh, August 1958. Camden, N. J., The Corporation, 1958. 25 l., 17 pl., processed.

Photosensitive Materials

54. Chalkley, Lyman: "Conditions for Projection Copying on Dye Cyanide Sensitized Materials," *Photographic Science and Engineering* 3:174-177. July-August, 1959.

Readers and Reading

55. *Reading for Life: Developing the College Student's Lifetime Reading Interest.* Edited with a Preface by Jacob M. Price. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press [c. 1959]. xi, 271 pp. (Record of the conference on "The Undergraduate and Life-Time Reading Interest," Ann Arbor, February 21-22, 1958.)

Scientific Information

56. International Conference on Scientific Information, Washington, D. C., November 16-21, 1958: *Preprints of Papers.* Washington: National Academy of Sciences-National Research Council, 1958. [xviii], 290, 207, 109, 139, 428, 123, 124 pp.

Standardization and Testing of Library Supplies, Equipment and Systems

57. Harwell, Richard B.: "The Library Technology Project," *ALA Bulletin*, 53:195-196, March, 1959.

58. Ottemiller, John H.: *Library Technology: A Feasibility Study. Report of the Director.* Chicago: American Library Association, 1958. 29 pp. processed.

59. — —: "A Program for Upgrading Systems and Procedures," *Library Journal*, 84:1041-1047, April 1, 1959.

NOTE ON ILLUSTRATIONS

The picture of the scholar at his book-wheel which appears on the cover and title-page is taken from Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine . . .*, Paris: 1588. The picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service.

The cards shown on the inside covers represent two Council-supported projects: the Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections at the Library of Congress, and *A Guide to Photocopied Historical Materials (in Manuscript) in the United States and Canada*, under preparation by Dr. Richard W. Hale, Jr., for the American Historical Society for publication in 1960. Also figuring in the design are pictures of paper making and type setting from Diderot's *Recueil de planches, sur les sciences, les arts libéraux, et les arts mécaniques, . . .*, Paris: 1763.

The photograph illustrating the limited size of early American library collections pictures the Eighteenth Century Room in the Harvey Firestone Memorial Library, Princeton University. The photograph, which suggests the seeming infinity of today's collections, was taken at the Library of Congress by George Lohr, who has designed this report.

The charts on the growth of library collections are the work of Dr. Laurence B. Heilprin.

Symbol of Reporting Institution [KU]
 Author Friends, Society of Richmond Dates 1854-1871
 Return to the Yearly Meeting
 Title Reports of the Indian Committee, 1854-1871
For Friends mission among the Shawnees of Kansas,
Members from members of Yearly meeting of Friends,
Highwood, Indiana
 Location of original material Ibid.
 Negative KU TYPE AMOUNT
 Positive 35 mm. 30 p.
 If positive, location of master negative.

If this material is restricted, checkhere ()

ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE U.S.S.R.,
 Leningrad
 Old Slavonic manuscripts: Kniga Gilmaia
 Tropni Papa Innokentii, Kniga Glagolemala
 Papa Innokentii; Kniga Glagolemata Legid-
 aries Ibid.
 N: KU 6 reels

Symbol of Reporting Institution [Hi-Ar]
 Author Cook, James Dates 1728-1778
 Return to the Sandwich
 Islands, 26 Nov., 1778, and subsequent proceedings
 Title to 6 Jan. 1778... Dates
 (See Over)
 Location of original material Public Records Office, London
 Negative TYPE AMOUNT
 Positive X Photostat 10 sheets
 If positive, location of master negative.

If this material is restricted, checkhere ()

Author Leningrad, Academy of Sciences
 of USSR, Library. MSS. written in Old Church
 Title Slavonic scripts and languages (see over)

Location of original material
 Negative^{XX} TYPE AMOUNT
 Positive 35 mm. 6 reels
 If positive, location of master negative.
 If this material is restricted, checkhere ()

Symbol of Reporting
 Author Cook, James
 Discovery of the Sand-
 Title Islands (See Over)

Location of original material Do
 Negative Hi
 Positive X
 If positive, location of master ne

If this material is restricted, che

FRANCE. ARCHIVES DES COLONIES. Série C-11-A
 Correspondance générale, Canada, 1540-1784,
 128 v. FRAN
 N: CaOOA 131 reels

CaOOA card 30. Archives

Symbol of Reporting Institution [CaOOA]
 Author France, Archives des Colonies
 Série C11-A
 Title Correspondance Générale Dates 1540-1784
Canada,
 Location of original material FRAN
 Negative CaOOA TYPE AMOUNT
 Positive 35 mm. 131 reels
 If positive, location of master negative.
 If this material is restricted, checkhere ()

FRIENDS, SOCIETY OF. RICHMOND YEARLY
 MEETING
 Reports of the Indian Committee re: Friends
 mission among the Shawnees of Kansas, 1854-
 1871 Ibid.
 N: KU

COOK, JAMES, 1728-1778
 Journals re: discovery of the Sandwich Islands,
 Jan. 18-Feb. 2, 1778; return to Sandwich Islands,
 Nov. 26, 1778-Jan. 6, 1779; supplementary logs,
 Series II, vv. 112-113 UKLPRO
 DCO: Hi-Ar

Hi-Ar cards (2)

Fig. 2

